

METHODOLOGY OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article describes oral speech, written speech, methods of developing students' speech, as well as what should be noted in students' speech development. At the end of the article, there is information about the directions of speech development.*

Keywords: *speech, written speech, oral speech, internal speech, external speech, voice tempo, word, phrase, connected speech.*

МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ РЕЧИ У УЧАЩИХСЯ

Аннотация. *В данной статье описывается устная речь, письменная речь, методы развития речи учащихся, а так же что следует отметить в развитии речи учащихся. В конце статьи есть информация о направлениях развития речи.*

Ключевые слова: *речь, письменная речь, устная речь, внутренняя речь, внешняя речь, темп голоса, слово, словосочетание, связная речь.*

INTRODUCTION

Through speech, a person expresses his feelings, desires, and understands others with the help of speech. Speech is a tool for the development of a person, communicating with people in society, showing his inner world, what kind of spiritual, cultured human he is.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

What is speech development? If the student and his/her language activities are taken into account, speech development means active and practical mastery of the language in all aspects (pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure, connected speech). In the case of a teacher, the development of speech means the use of methods and techniques that help students acquire active language pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure, and connected speech.

Types of speech:

Oral speech

Written speech

Inner speech

External speech

There are 2 types of speech used to express an idea. They are oral and written speech. The teacher should be able to form and develop both in students.

RESULTS

Oral speech is a way of speaking. It mainly uses tones and gestures.

In oral speech, he does not use complex sentences or conjunctions much. Written speech is more complicated. In written speech, special attention is paid to the correct spelling of words, the use of punctuation marks, and the structure of sentences. Everyone thinks before he speaks, that is, he thinks and then he speaks. This speech is called internal speech. Internal speech is not broadcast and is not recorded anywhere. External speech is voiced or written with graphic symbols, always directed to the second person.

It is necessary to educate the students about the content of the speech, voice tempo, speaking with the correct emphasis on the letters in the words, high and low voice, breathing and

exhalation processes. Special attention should be paid to the pronunciation of letters (s, z),(j, sh, ch),(l, r).

DISCUSSION

In the development of students' speech, the use of methods of creating a story based on a picture, the teacher reading the story and telling the students by heart what they heard will help the student's speech to be more perfect and fluent. One of the most useful ways to develop student speech is for the teacher to start the story.

Students think in the process of continuing the story, expand their imagination and learn to use words correctly. Later, he gradually learns to use similar words.

Three directions are clearly distinguished in the development of speech:

- 1) work on words;
- 2) working on phrases and sentences;
- 3) work on connected speech.

CONCLUSIONS

Lexicology is a linguistic base for working on words, phrases and sentences (together with phraseology and stylistics), morphology, syntax serve and connected speech is based on logic, literary studies and complex syntactic integrity is based on linguistics. There are four conditions for consistency in speech development that is, the consistency, perspective, and variety of the exercises are ensured by the implementation of the skill of subordinating various types of exercises to a common goal.

First of all, the teacher should be an example for students to form speech. In the classroom and extra-curricular processes, in the schoolyard, he should always speak in accordance with the standards of literary language, and should not use dialect-related words and phrases. The teacher should write in students' notebooks, all documents on the basis of husnikhat and following the rules of spelling.

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